

1 **Microenvironment tailoring for electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction: Effects of interfacial** 2 **structure on controlling activity and selectivity**

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13 **ABSTRACT**

14 The performance of the electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction reaction (CO₂RR) is highly dependent on the
15 microenvironment around the cathode. Despite efforts to optimize the microenvironment by modifying
16 nanostructured catalysts or microporous gas diffusion electrodes, their inherent disorder presents a
17 significant challenge to understanding how interfacial structure arrangement within the electrode governs
18 the microenvironment for CO₂RR. This knowledge gap limits fundamental understanding of CO₂RR while
19 also hindering efforts to enhance CO₂RR selectivity and activity. In this work, we investigate this
20 knowledge gap using a tunable system featuring hierarchical Cu nanowire arrays that possess adjustable
21 microgroove dimensions. Adjusting the NAM structure tunes multiple synergistic effects in the
22 microenvironment, which include stabilization of the microwetting state, confinement of CO*,
23 improvement to local CO₂ concentration, and modulation of the local pH. Notably, using mass transport
24 modeling, we quantify the role of the gas-liquid-solid interface in boosting local CO₂ concentrations within
25 several microns of the interface itself. Leveraging these effects, we elucidate how CO* and H*
26 competitively occupy active sites, influencing reaction pathways toward multicarbon products based on
27 tuning the microenvironment. Consequently, we provide new insights into why the optimized

28 configuration significantly increased CO₂RR activity by 690% (as normalized by electrochemical active
29 surface area), C₂₊ product selectivity by 72%, and Faradaic efficiency by 36%, compared to CO₂RR with
30 hydrophobic Cu foil. Based on these insights, our findings unlock new opportunities to engineer the
31 CO₂RR microenvironment through the rational organization of hierarchical interface materials in gas
32 diffusion electrodes towards improved CO₂RR selectivity and activity.

33 **Introduction**

34 With the reliance on fossil fuel combustion-based energy systems, carbon dioxide (CO₂) accumulation
35 in the atmosphere has contributed to a greenhouse effect, driving global climate change, which has drawn
36 increasing attention for the past several decades.¹ To recycle CO₂ and mitigate its emissions, the
37 electrochemical carbon dioxide reduction reaction (CO₂RR) provides an effective strategy for a carbon-
38 neutral future and climate change elimination.²⁻³ Moreover, as an electrocatalytic process, CO₂RR pairs
39 well with renewable electricity sources, such as solar, tidal, or wind, enabling the sustainable production
40 of value-added fuels and chemicals.⁴⁻⁵ In particular, Cu-based catalysts for CO₂RR have received
41 considerable attention because Cu is uniquely active for carbon-carbon (C-C) coupling to generate multi-
42 carbon products, including hydrocarbons and oxygenated products.⁶⁻⁷ Consequently, tremendous efforts
43 have focused on designing Cu-based catalysts with optimized adsorbate energies of key intermediates by
44 manipulating their surface morphology,⁸⁻¹³ size,¹⁴⁻¹⁸ grain boundaries,¹⁹⁻²² and chemical composition,²³⁻²⁶
45 thereby promoting their intrinsic activity and selectivity in terms of Faradaic efficiency (FE) for CO₂RR.
46 However, beyond the intrinsic properties of catalysts, systematic approaches to optimize the local
47 microenvironment at the catalyst-electrolyte interface have been elusive, even though they also play a
48 crucial role in determining the product selectivity and activity of CO₂RR.²⁷⁻²⁸

49 Although the microenvironment is critical for determining CO₂RR selectivity and activity, the
50 connection between the microenvironment and interfacial structure within an electrode remains an area

51 that is relatively poorly understood. This critical knowledge gap limits the ability to rationally adjust the
52 microenvironment to optimize CO₂RR selectivity and activity by adjusting electrode structure.²⁹ Recent
53 studies have demonstrated that incorporating catalyst–electrolyte–gas triple-phase interfaces can
54 concentrate CO₂ reactants and accommodate a local alkaline environment to enhance the CO₂RR activity
55 and tune product selectivity.³⁰⁻³² Thus, the implemented strategies have focused on constructing
56 hydrophobic nanostructured surfaces with water-resistant and CO₂-trapping functionalities,³³⁻³⁶ and on
57 employing porous gas diffusion electrodes (GDEs) that have Janus contacts, interfacing with the
58 electrolyte on one side and the flowing CO₂ gas on the other.³⁷⁻³⁹ Nevertheless, so far, these nanofabricated
59 Cu electrodes and microporous GDEs possess high degrees of disorder as well as high variability in shape
60 and size,^{40,41} making it challenging to quantify how the catalyst structural arrangement regulates the mass
61 transport of reactant species, the CO₂RR microenvironment, and consequently CO₂RR performance.²⁹
62 Therefore, model systems are urgently needed. Such model systems should be amenable to 3D transport
63 modeling with tunable structures that can precisely probe the relationship between the structure, interfaces,
64 transport, microenvironment, and performance to gain additional insights into the design principles of
65 catalyst arrangement and GDEs toward the ultimate goal of understanding how CO₂RR performance can
66 improve in terms of both selectivity and activity.

67 In this work, we unveil the roles of synergistic phenomena using our tunable nanowire arrays with
68 microgrooves (NAMs) based cathodes as a model platform, which we characterize via a suite of techniques
69 that include laser scanning confocal microscopy, three-dimensional mass transfer modeling, and
70 electrochemical characterization techniques. The microgrooves of NAM-30 structure exerts an upwards
71 Laplace pressure to stabilize the wetting state of the gas-liquid-solid interface for favorable CO₂ transport.
72 Based on this, we show increased availability of CO₂ at two-phase liquid-solid interfaces within several
73 microns of the 3-phase gas-liquid-solid interface, allowing Cu sites at both interfaces to have more access

74 to CO₂. Moreover, the superior CO* confinement at the top of nanowire bundles also leads to more facile
75 C-C coupling to form C₂ products. In addition to this, we find that adjusting the structure of the NAM-
76 based cathode can tune the local pH, which can allow H* to participate in hydrogenation steps within
77 CO₂RR rather than HER in the presence of improved availability of CO₂ and CO. Taken together, we
78 show that tuning the structure of the cathode interfaces can tailor the CO₂RR microenvironment to achieve
79 improved CO₂RR performance. These performance improvements include a 690% increase in the
80 electrochemical active surface area (ECSA)-normalized activity, a 72% increase in the C₂₊ product
81 selectivity, and a 36% increase in the Faradaic efficiency for CO₂RR as compared to the CO₂RR
82 performance of hydrophobic Cu foil. These insights reveal essential new design concepts for improving
83 CO₂RR selectivity and activity by tuning the CO₂RR microenvironment, which informs efforts to improve
84 CO₂RR performance and scalability.

85 **Results**

86 **Design and characterization of NAMs**

87 Fig. 1a shows a schematic drawing of our designed tunable hierarchical model structure, which consists
88 of microgrooves and gradient nanostructures. Solely by adjusting the diameter of the nanowires, both the
89 spacing between nanowires and the opening angle of the microgrooves can be tuned accordingly because
90 of the soft nature of the Cu nanowires that can bend and agglomerate into nanowire bundles. Based on
91 functionality, we divide the structure into three zones: the microgroove, the densely packed nanostructure
92 at the top, and the sparsely arranged nanostructure at the bottom. The microgrooves exert an upward
93 Laplace force to stabilize the electrolyte–gas interface for a stable Cassie–Baxter wetting state,⁴⁰ which
94 not only enhances gaseous reactant diffusion from the bottom gas layer to the top reaction zone but also
95 traps the produced CO in the gas pocket as a CO reservoir. The sparsely arranged nanostructure at the
96 bottom is designed to reduce the lateral mass transfer resistance of the gaseous reactant. Conversely, the

97 densely packed nanostructures at the top synergistically confine the CO* and promote C-C coupling for
98 multicarbon products.

99
100 **Fig. 1 | Schematic illustration of the tunable hierarchical structure design and corresponding**
101 **preparation strategy for enhancing CO₂ mass transfer and optimizing the local microenvironment.**

102 **a**, Liquid–solid–gas three-phase schematic highlighting that by tuning hierarchically structures, the
103 wetting state and the mass transport near the liquid–gas interface are adaptively changed. The
104 microgrooves exert upward Laplace pressure and stabilize the Cassie-Baxter wetting state, which enhances
105 the diffusion of the gaseous reactants from the bottom gas layer to the top reaction zone. Sparsely arranged
106 nanowires at the bottom assist in reducing the lateral diffusion resistance of gas molecules. Conversely,
107 densely packed nanowires at the top confine the key intermediate CO* and facilitate C-C coupling for
108 multicarbon products. **b**, Schematic illustration of the realization method of hierarchically structured
109 NAMs.

110 We fabricated templated nanowire arrays with microgrooves (NAMs) through a two-step template-
111 assisted electrodeposition method,⁴¹ as depicted in Fig. 1b. In the first step, the anodic alumina oxide
112 (AAO) template is attached onto a Cu foil by electrodeposition at -0.8 V for 60 min, as shown in

113 Supplementary Fig. 1. During this electrodeposition process, short nanowires are formed in the holes of
114 AAO to fix the AAO template on the Cu surface. In the second step, the nanowires grow longer by
115 electrodeposition for another 60 min. Then, the AAO template is removed by immersion in a 2 M NaOH
116 solution. Finally, treatment with an *n*-octadecanethiol solution confers superhydrophobicity to the NAMs.
117 In the following discussion, 'Cu foil' refers to the planar Cu foil after the same hydrophobic treatment with
118 *n*-octadecanethiol solution.

119 Our study employed three variants of commercial AAO templates to fabricate nanowire arrays with
120 different structural parameters. As depicted in the SEM images of these AAO templates (Supplementary
121 Fig. 2), the pores of all the AAO templates show a hexagonal pattern with the same pore pitch of
122 approximately 450 nm but varying pore diameters measuring 200, 300, and 400 nm, respectively. The
123 geometries of the as-fabricated NAMs with different structural parameters are shown in Figs. 2a-c. The
124 nanowires undergo bending and aggregation due to the surface tension of water upon removal from the
125 NaOH solution. Consequently, nanowire bundles and microgrooves form, leading to a notable gradient
126 structure in that the nanowires at the top are densely packed, while those at the bottom are sparsely
127 arranged, as shown in Fig. 2a. As the diameter of the nanowire increases, its rigidity improves, leading to
128 a decrease in both the opening angle of the microgrooves and the spacing between the bottom nanowires.
129 In contrast, the spacings between the nanowires at the top remain comparable, as shown in Figs. 2b and c.
130 The NAMs with nanowire diameters of 200, 300, and 400 nm exhibit opening angles of 30, 10, and 0°,
131 respectively, for the microgrooves and are thus termed NAM-30, NAM-10, and NAM-0, respectively.
132 Initially, the as-fabricated NAM samples are hydrophilic, having contact angles smaller than 90°
133 (Supplementary Fig. 3). However, after hydrophobic treatment, the materials exhibit superhydrophobicity,
134 with contact angles exceeding 150°, as shown in Fig. 2d. Furthermore, X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns
135 (Supplementary Fig. 4) show that all the samples have the same three peaks at 43.3°, 50.4°, and 74.1°.

136 corresponding to face-centered cubic Cu(111), Cu(200), and Cu(220), respectively, which demonstrates
137 that the electrodeposition and hydrophobic treatment processes do not alter the crystal structure of Cu.

138

139 **Fig. 2 | Characterization of NAMs.** Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of NAMs with opening
140 angles of **a**, 30°, **b**, 10°, and **c**, 0° for the microgrooves. The first and second columns show the nanowire
141 arrays with microgrooves from the top and side views, respectively. The third and fourth columns show
142 the densely packed nanowires at the top and sparsely arranged nanowires at the bottom, respectively. **d**,
143 The contact angles for the superhydrophobic NAMs and hydrophobic Cu foil. **e**, High-resolution XPS Cu
144 2*p* spectra of NAMs before (blue) and after (red) hydrophobic treatment. **f**, High-resolution XPS S 2*p*
145 spectra of NAMs before (blue) and after (red) hydrophobic treatment.

146 The chemical states of the NAMs were further characterized by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy
147 (XPS), as shown in Fig. 2e. Both treated and untreated NAM-30 exhibit the same Cu (0/I) state, which is

148 evident as two peaks at 933.3 (Cu 2p_{3/2}) and 952.2 eV (Cu 2p_{1/2}). It should be noted that the minor peaks
149 at 934.5/944.1 eV and 955.0/962.8 eV for the hydrophilic NAMs can be attributed to Cu (II) 2p_{3/2} and Cu
150 (II) 2p_{1/2}, respectively. However, after the hydrophobic treatment involving alkane thiolation, Cu (II) oxide
151 is removed from the surface, leaving Cu (I)–S bonds,⁴² which is consistent with the peak of S 2p at 162.2
152 eV shown in Fig. 2f. The energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) mapping of NAM-30 is also shown in
153 Supplementary Fig. 5, which is consistent with the XPS results. All of these results imply that the designed
154 Cu NAMs possess homogeneous physical and chemical properties while the varying structural parameters
155 were successfully obtained.

156 **Electrochemical CO₂ conversion**

157 To evaluate the influence of the structure on the electrocatalytic performance of NAMs, the
158 electrochemical reduction of CO₂ was investigated in an H-cell with a three-electrode configuration, where
159 Ag/AgCl was the reference electrode, Pt foil was the counter electrode, and CO₂-saturated 0.1 M KHCO₃
160 was the electrolyte. The FEs of the products at applied potentials between -1.0 and -1.3 V vs. the reversible
161 hydrogen electrode (RHE) for NAM-30 are presented in Fig. 3a. The selectivity of NAM-10, NAM-0, and
162 Cu foil is depicted in Supplementary Fig. 6. With increasingly negative applied potentials, the FEs of CO
163 and HCOO⁻ decrease, while the FEs of CH₄, C₂H₄, and CH₃CH₂OH increase. Although all three NAMs
164 achieve their optimal total FE for the CO₂RR at -1.1 V vs. RHE, this value is further improved with the
165 increased prominence of microgrooves, as NAM-30 achieves the highest FE for CO₂RR at 90.3%.
166 Specifically, as the most valuable products, the FEs of C₂₊ compounds exhibit the highest values at -1.2
167 V vs. RHE for all NAMs. For a detailed comparison, the CO₂RR selectivity among all NAMs and Cu foil
168 is depicted in Fig. 3b. The FEs of the H₂ and C₁ products increase when the opening angle of the grooves
169 decreases, whereas the FEs of the C₂₊ products show the opposite trend. Consequently, NAM-30 achieves
170 the lowest FE of H₂ (13.1%) and the highest FE of C₂₊ products (55.7%), respectively, indicating a 64%

171 improvement in reducing the FE to competing reaction (*i.e.*, hydrogen evolution reaction (HER))
172 suppression and a 72% improvement in C₂₊ production when compared to the pristine Cu foil. In fact, the
173 CO₂RR-to-HER ratio is dramatically increased from 2.1 to 6.7 by increasing the opening angle of the
174 microgrooves and the bottom nanowire spacing, as shown in Fig. 3c. Simultaneously, the C₂₊-to-C₁ ratio
175 is also effectively tuned from 0.6 to 1.7 by optimizing the structural parameters of the NAMs (Fig. 3d).
176 These results suggest that the arrangement of catalyst structures plays a critical role in tuning the selectivity
177 of CO₂RR; the increased prominence of microgrooves and the bottom nanowire spacing not only inhibits
178 HER but also directs the reaction pathways toward C₂₊ products.

179 In addition to selectivity, another important metric in CO₂RR is the current density (current normalized
180 by the geometric electrode area, 1 cm²), especially the partial current density, as presented in
181 Supplementary Figs. 7 and 8. Interestingly, the partial current densities of CO₂RR and HER also strongly
182 depend on the structural geometries of the samples. Compared to that of hydrophobic Cu foil, the partial
183 current density of NAM-30 exhibited a 145% improvement in CO₂RR and 50% suppression in HER. The
184 superhydrophobic wettability facilitates gas trapping beneath the nanowires, improving gas-phase CO₂
185 reactant supply in CO₂RR and reducing the contact area between the electrode and electrolyte liquid for
186 HER.

187

188 **Fig. 3 | CO₂RR performance of NAMs in a CO₂-saturated 0.1 M KHCO₃ electrolyte. a,** Product
 189 selectivity of NAM-30 as a function of applied potential. **b,** Product distribution of all samples at -1.2 V
 190 vs. RHE. **c,** Ratio of carbon reduction products to hydrogen at -1.2 V vs. RHE. **d,** Ratio of C₂+ products to
 191 C₁ products at -1.2 V vs. RHE. **e,** Calculation of C_{dI} based on the current densities and scan rates of the
 192 corresponding cyclic voltammetry (CV) curves. **f,** Comparison of the geometric area- and ECSA-
 193 normalized partial current density of CO₂RR for all samples at -1.2 V vs. RHE.

194 To further verify this observation, we measured the electrochemical active surface area (ECSA) of the
 195 NAMs. Supplementary Fig. 9 displays the corresponding cyclic voltammetry (CV) curves, while the
 196 calculated C_{dI} and ECSA based on the current values and the scan rates are listed in Supplementary Table
 197 1. As shown in Fig. 3e, the ECSA decreases with increasing opening angle of the microgrooves,
 198 demonstrating a smaller overall contact area between the electrode surface and the electrolyte owing to
 199 the replacement of trapped gas within the nanowire arrays. Furthermore, the ECSA-normalized current
 200 density of CO₂RR on NAM-30 significantly increased to 162 mA/cm²_{ECSA}, demonstrating a 7.9-fold
 201 enhancement compared with that of hydrophobic Cu foil (Fig. 3f). On the other hand, for NAM-0, even
 202 though the geometric area-normalized partial current density of CO₂RR is greater than that of Cu foil, the

203 lower ECSA-normalized partial current density implies that the better apparent activity originates from its
204 enlarged contact area rather than from the increase in the intrinsic activity.⁴³

205 **Visualization of the microscopic wetting state**

206 To contextualize the correlation between NAM structure and CO₂RR performance, we have further
207 investigated the wetting state of each NAM to understand the nature of the microenvironment during
208 CO₂RR conditions. Although all the as-fabricated NAMs are nominally superhydrophobic, they exhibit
209 different macroscopic wetting states during the CO₂RR process, as shown in Fig. 4a. For NAM-30, a gas
210 layer is trapped between the electrode and electrolyte. This demonstrates its stable superhydrophobicity,
211 which sustains a macroscale Cassie-Baxter wetting state during the reaction. In contrast, in the cases of
212 NAM-10 and NAM-0, separated small and large bubbles instead of a continuous gas layer form at the
213 surface, indicating a wetting transition from the Cassie-Baxter state to the Wenzel state.

214 To further visualize the microscopic wetting state of the NAMs, we observed the shape of the gas-
215 liquid-solid interfaces using laser scanning confocal microscopy, as shown in Fig. 4b. For NAM-30, when
216 the focus is moving from the top of the nanowire arrays (height from the substrate (h) = 10 μm) down to
217 h = 8 μm , a strong reflection of the liquid-gas interface located among the nanowire bundles appears,
218 confirming that the liquid-gas interface is continuous and very stable with an approximately 2 μm
219 intrusion depth of the electrolyte into the nanowire arrays. However, the same region of NAM-10 is
220 partially flooded with a discontinuous liquid-gas interface, and the electrolyte is flooded throughout the
221 nanowire arrays for NAM-0. At the bottom of the nanowire arrays, the primary signal is from the reflection
222 of the Cu base for NAM-30 and NAM-10 due to the absence of electrolyte, which is distinguished from
223 the Wenzel wetting state as evidenced by the complete red color of the dyed electrolyte in NAM-0.

224

225 **Fig. 4 | Characterization of gas-liquid-solid interfaces for NAMs during CO₂RR.** **a**, Optical
 226 observation of the macroscopic wetting states of NAMs in CO₂RR. **b**, Confocal microscopy images of

227 NAM-30, NAM-10, and NAM-0, respectively. The slices are displayed from a top view and selected along
228 the height direction of the nanowires. The red signal represents the emission light of the rhodamine
229 dissolved in the electrolyte, while the green signal is the reflection of the excitation laser light from gas-
230 liquid-solid interfaces. **c-d**, Schematic illustration of the gas-liquid-solid three-phase interfaces of NAM-
231 30 and NAM-0 in CO₂RR. **e**, Charge of CO oxidation derived from chronoamperometric curves.

232 The different statuses of the gas-liquid-solid interfaces in the nanowire arrays of NAM-30 and NAM-
233 0 are schematically illustrated in Figs. 4c and d, respectively. NAM-30 is in a stable Cassie-Baxter wetting
234 state, with a gas layer in a thickness of 8 μm trapped between the electrolyte and nanowire arrays during
235 CO₂RR. In contrast, NAM-0 exhibited a Wenzel state, where the electrolyte completely wetted the
236 nanowire arrays. As a transition state between the Cassie-Baxter and Wenzel states, NAM-10 is
237 characterized by a non-uniform partial wetting state. The drastic difference between wetting states in each
238 NAM sample has important implications for the CO₂RR microenvironment.

239 **CO confinement effect**

240 Water is a critical source of the H* intermediate for both HER and CO₂RR.⁴⁴ Very recently, during the
241 preparation of the present work, it has been shown that the availability of H* can be effectively tailored
242 by controlling the microwetting state.⁴⁵ In addition, the availability of another intermediate (*i.e.*, CO*)
243 also plays a dominant role in determining the C-C coupling and hence the C₂₊ product selectivity, which
244 is then quantified by in situ CO stripping (*i.e.*, the CO source is produced by CO₂RR). The CO stripping
245 curves presented in Supplementary Fig. 10 reveal that CO oxidation occurs at ~0.2 V vs. RHE for both
246 NAM-30 and NAM-0.⁴⁶ However, NAM-30 exhibited a significantly greater peak intensity for CO
247 oxidation than did NAM-0. This enhanced performance is even more pronounced when normalized by the
248 ECSA. As shown in Supplementary Fig. 11, NAM-30 shows an impressive 18-fold increase in CO density
249 compared to NAM-0. To gain a more comprehensive understanding, CO stripping chronoamperometry
250 (Supplementary Fig. 12) was then employed to reveal the CO availability via both spatial and temporal

251 metrics. The CO stripping chronoamperometry results before and after the double layer charge correction
252 are shown in Supplementary Figs. 13 and 14, respectively. As expected, the depletion time of CO on
253 NAM-30 (24 s) is 2.2 times that on NAM-0 (11 s), owing to the enhanced CO supply from the confined
254 CO. In addition, throughout the entire process, the CO oxidation current density of NAM-30 consistently
255 surpassed that of NAM-0. Taken together, these findings suggest that the NAM-30 structure promotes CO
256 availability. Furthermore, Fig. 4e shows a comparison of the charge transferred during CO oxidation
257 between NAM-30 and NAM-0. NAM-30 exhibited a CO oxidation charge of 2.5 mC/cm², which was 4-
258 fold greater than that of NAM-0 (0.5 mC/cm²). This substantial increase in CO availability further provides
259 insights into the cause for the marked increase in C₂₊ production observed in NAM-30, as CO availability
260 is well known to promote C₂₊ product formation.⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹

261 **Mass transport and the microenvironment in NAMs**

262 As mentioned earlier, mass transfer and the microenvironment (*e.g.*, local CO₂ concentration and pH)
263 around catalysts can significantly affect product distribution and activity.⁵⁰⁻⁵² Based on our direct
264 observation of the composite interfaces, we further numerically model in situ three-dimensional (3D) mass
265 transfer processes on NAMs to illustrate the role of the microenvironment in the reaction pathways of
266 CO₂RR. Herein, we utilized the finite-element method on the COMSOL Multiphysics[®] platform to
267 perform a 3D simulation study. A schematic diagram of the physical model is displayed in Fig. 5a. This
268 process involves the mass transport processes, carbonate species equilibria of OH⁻, CO₂, HCO₃⁻, and
269 CO₃²⁻, the local hydrolysis of K⁺ in the electrolyte phase, and mass consumption and generation during
270 CO₂RR.⁵³⁻⁵⁴ To perform this analysis, we consider the following five assumptions and boundary
271 conditions (Supplementary Fig. 15): (1) The mass transfer processes are in a steady state, and diffusion
272 occurs near the surface with negligible convection. (2) The CO₂RR occurs at the liquid–solid interface, so
273 the CO₂RR-induced mass consumption (CO₂) and generation (OH⁻) can be represented by a reaction

274 boundary at this interface; thus, electron transfer and mass conservation are correlated with the measured
275 current density and FEs. A zero-flux condition is imposed on nonreactive species at the liquid–solid
276 interface. (3) The top boundary is treated with a constant species concentration as that of the bulk
277 conditions. (4) The boundary of the gas–liquid interface for NAM-30 is regarded with a constant
278 concentration of CO₂, as a stable CO₂ gas layer is underneath its nanowires. The detailed assumptions,
279 boundary conditions, settings, and model parameters are provided in “Computational Modeling” in the
280 Methods section and Supplementary Tables 2-5.

281 The computational results of the spatial distributions of the CO₂ concentration and pH for NAMs with
282 different interfacial structures are shown in Figs. 5b-e and Supplementary Figs. 16-18. The CO₂
283 concentration and pH data extracted from the contour maps are further intuitively compared in Figs. 5f
284 and g. Enabled by the Cassie–Baxter wetting state of NAM-30, bidirectional CO₂ transport from both the
285 bottom gas layer and the top bulk to the nanowires is observed, as shown by the streamlines in Fig. 5b.
286 Compared with the nanowire bundles, the microgrooves show significantly reduced CO₂ transport
287 resistance, enabling a small CO₂ concentration gradient and a large CO₂ concentration (> 33.5 mol/m³) in
288 the grooves. Consequently, the small diffusion length from the microgroove to the central nanowire bundle
289 further facilitates rapid lateral diffusion and a high local CO₂ concentration throughout the whole nanowire
290 reactive interface, with a value of at least 33.0 mol/m³. Conversely, the Wenzel wetting state of NAM-0
291 coupled with the narrow spacing between the nanowires results in a near one-directional transport of CO₂
292 (Fig. 5c). The CO₂ concentration in NAM-0 was lower than that in NAM-30, with a larger concentration
293 gradient. The highest and lowest concentration values for NAM-0 were 24.3 and 10.0 mol/m³, respectively.
294 Overall, this analysis reveals the favorable role of the gas-phase interface within the cathode in increasing
295 the local CO₂ concentration in the proximity of the gas-liquid-solid interface, in addition to only the

296 specific location of the interface itself. This result is of relevance to the ongoing debate regarding the role
297 of three-phase (gas-liquid-solid) versus two-phase (liquid-solid) interfaces in CO₂RR.⁵⁵⁻⁵⁷

298 Additionally, in terms of local pH, NAM-30 also has a moderate pH with a slight variation between 9.6
299 and 10.4 (Fig. 5d), which can be ascribed to the short diffusion distance from the gas-liquid interface to
300 the top of the nanowires. However, for NAM-0, both the near one-dimensional and longer diffusion
301 distances result in a large pH gradient ranging from 8.5 (top) to 11.7 (bottom) along the nanowire height
302 (Fig. 5e). Therefore, the simulation results highlight the effect of the interfacial structure on both the spatial
303 distribution of the CO₂ concentration and the pH, and both of these gradients are important aspects of the
304 microenvironment that can determine selectivity and activity for CO₂RR.

305

306 **Fig. 5 | 3D numerical simulation of the mass transfer process on NAMs in CO₂RR.** **a**, Physical model
 307 schematic of the mass transfer processes in CO₂RR. **b**, Contour maps of the CO₂ concentration profile on
 308 NAM-30 in 3D and 2D views of the left and right columns, respectively. The 2D plot is the cross-sectional
 309 view labeled by a dashed line in the 3D map. The streamlines indicate the direction of CO₂ transfer. **c**,
 310 Contour maps of the CO₂ concentration profile of NAM-0. **d**, Contour maps of the pH of NAM-30. The
 311 streamlines indicate the direction of H⁺ transfer. **e**, Contour maps of pH on NAM-0. **f**, Local concentration
 312 distribution of CO₂ along the height direction of the nanowires. **g**, Local pH distribution along the height
 313 direction of the nanowires. **h**, Comparison of the spatially averaged concentrations of CO₂ and pH among
 314 the NAMs. All the results were acquired at -1.2 V vs. RHE.

315 Based on these deep quantitative insights into the local microenvironment, we can determine the
316 underlying causes for the selectivity trends observed in our CO₂RR performance data. Here, the spatially
317 averaged CO₂ concentration and pH in the $0 < h < 10$ μm zone for NAMs were selected as representative
318 descriptors (Fig. 5h) to deduce the correlation between the microenvironment and reaction pathways for
319 different products. It has been widely accepted that the concentration of CO₂ at the reactive interface
320 influences CO₂ adsorption and that concurrent proton-electron coupled transfers lead to the formation of
321 the key CO* intermediate,^{45, 58} which subsequently desorbs from the surface to form CO or further
322 undergoes C-C coupling and protonation steps to form C₂₊ products. On the other hand, the local pH
323 determines the rate of water dissociation and the formation of H*, whose competitive occupation with
324 CO₂RR intermediates on active sites and influences the electrochemical pathway that occurs, which is
325 responsible for the total FE and variations in CO₂RR selectivity. Therefore, it is reasonable that the
326 variations in CO* and H* availability caused by the local concentration of CO₂ and pH via wetting state
327 change is one of the critical reasons for the observed selectivity. First, the high local concentration of CO₂
328 and CO* in NAM-30 enables a high occupation ratio of Cu active sites by CO₂ product intermediates like
329 CO*, which inhibits competing H* adsorption and hydrogen production, in good agreement with the
330 lowest FE of HER occurring on NAM-30. Subsequently, the CO* prefers to undergo protonation as part
331 of the hydrocarbons production rather than being directly desorbed from Cu-based catalysts due to a more
332 neutral environment induced by NAM-30, because a moderate pH is beneficial for electron-proton transfer
333 to access the CHOH* intermediate, which is consistent with recent reports on CO reduction and the
334 mechanistic prediction of pH effects.⁵⁹⁻⁶⁰ The results also imply that under these conditions when the CO₂
335 concentration is high, H* preferentially participates in protonation in CO₂RR rather than HER. This is also
336 consistent with recent results showing a tendency for CO₂RR exhibit higher selectivity versus water
337 reduction as the pH value becomes more neutral.⁶¹ More importantly, the easy access to high CO*

338 coverage derived from the high local CO₂ concentration is a crucial factor for C-C coupling, contributing
339 to the improved FE for C₂₊ products on NAM-30⁴⁸. In contrast, NAM-0, which has the lowest CO₂
340 concentration and the highest local pH, has the highest selectivity for HCOO⁻. Here, NAM-0 has the lowest
341 FE of C₂₊ products because of insufficient CO* intermediate density and limited proton availability.
342 Furthermore, the CO₂ concentration and pH of the hydrophobic Cu foil and NAM-10, together with their
343 CO₂RR selectivity, are also consistent with these trends. These results imply that the competition for both
344 the spatial occupation of active sites and the subsequent reaction pathway followed by H* are highly
345 dependent on the local CO₂ concentration and pH. This finding underscores the importance of these factors
346 and their synergistic interactions in designing the arrangement and interface of catalysts, support materials,
347 and electrodes for efficient electrocatalytic CO₂ conversion. These insights can inform efforts to boost the
348 performance of CO₂RR in applied systems in terms of selectivity and activity.

349 **Discussion**

350 In summary, this work clearly demonstrates the tunability of CO₂RR activity and selectivity by tailoring
351 the reaction microenvironment near the catalyst surface by adjusting of the interfacial structure of the
352 catalyst. To achieve this, we developed and modeled a quasiperiodic system with hierarchically structured
353 nanowire arrays that are encircled by microgrooves, and this hierarchical structure can overcome previous
354 challenges posed by the barriers limiting study of disordered electrodes for CO₂RR. Within this structure,
355 the microgrooves enhance CO₂ transport to reaction sites, and the nanowire bundles, which possess an
356 inter-nanowire spacing gradient from bottom to top, simultaneously assist the mass transport of reactants
357 and confine CO* intermediates to promote C-C coupling for multicarbon products. As a result, NAM-30
358 achieved significant enhancements in the ECSA-normalized activity (690%), faradaic efficiency (36%),
359 and C₂₊ product selectivity (72%) for CO₂RR, when compared to those of hydrophobic Cu foil. Using
360 laser scanning confocal microscopy, we visually demonstrated how this well-controlled hierarchical

361 morphology helps maintain the Cassie–Baxter wetting state and stabilizes the supply of gaseous reactants
362 (such as CO₂) to the gas–liquid–solid interfaces for NAM-30. The closely packed nanowires in NAM-30,
363 which facilitate the high availability of CO due to the confinement effect, contribute to improved C₂₊
364 product selectivity, as confirmed by CO stripping experiments. Leveraging the periodicity of the
365 interfacial geometries in our model system, we successfully developed 3D mass transfer models of the
366 NAMs to quantify the relationship between the reaction microenvironment and performance. Notably, our
367 analysis of the mass transfer models reveals the beneficial effect of the gas-liquid-solid interface on
368 boosting CO₂ concentrations in the local microenvironment within several microns of the interface itself,
369 which can inform the current understanding of the interplay of the gas-liquid-solid and liquid-solid
370 interfaces for CO₂RR. Combining all of these investigations, we show that several effects influence the
371 competitive spatial occupation of active sites and determine the subsequent reaction pathway of H* and
372 CO*. These observed effects include the high concentration of CO₂ present in the gas pocket, the high
373 availability of CO facilitated by CO confinement between nanowires, and the moderate local pH in NAM-
374 30. These synergistic effects influence the reaction pathways to enhance selectivity toward C₂₊ products
375 and reduce the competing hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) in NAM-30. This study provides valuable
376 insights into how hierarchical structure arrangements impact interfacial wetting, microenvironment, and
377 (ultimately) CO₂RR performance. These design principles can be applied to other state-of-the-art catalyst
378 systems and practical gas diffusion layers for CO₂RR. Furthermore, our combined approach using laser
379 scanning confocal microscopy and 3D finite element simulation is an excellent example of a simple,
380 accurate, and helpful strategy for studying and developing design rules to optimize multiphase catalysis
381 systems.

382 **Methods**

383 **NAMs preparation**

384 Superhydrophobic nanowire arrays with microgrooves (NAMs) were fabricated on Cu foil using a two-
385 step double-pass anodic alumina oxide (AAO) template-assisted electrodeposition method. The Cu foils
386 (99.999% purity, $0.2 \times 20 \times 10$ mm) used in the experiments were polished with 800, 1500, 2000, 3000,
387 and 5000 mesh sandpaper in sequence. After mechanical polishing, it was electropolished in 85%
388 phosphoric acid at 3 V against a counter electrode for 1 min. Before utilization, the Cu foil was
389 supersonically cleaned with acetone, ethanol, and deionized water for 5 min in sequence and then dried
390 with nitrogen gas. A schematic illustration of the custom-made setup for the first step of electrodeposition
391 is shown in Supplementary Fig. 1. The plating solution was composed of copper pyrophosphate
392 ($\text{Cu}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Sigma–Aldrich), potassium pyrophosphate ($\text{K}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Sigma–Aldrich), ammonium
393 citrate tribasic ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{O}_7$, Sigma–Aldrich, 97%), and deionized water (Milli-Q, $>18 \text{ M}\Omega \text{ cm}$) with a
394 mass ratio of 6:25:2:100. A double-pass AAO template (Bonding Chemical) wetted with electroplating
395 solution was placed on Cu foil. A filter paper completely wetted by the plating solution was placed on the
396 AAO template to store the plating solution. The counter Cu foil was placed over the filter paper to form a
397 2-electrode system. The first step of electrodeposition was carried out at -0.8 V for 60 min. In the second
398 step, electrodeposition was carried out in a single cell with three electrodes for another 60 min. The applied
399 potential was -0.8 V vs. Ag/AgCl. After electroplating, the cathode was rinsed and immersed in 2 M NaOH
400 (Sigma–Aldrich, 98%) solution for 3 hours to completely dissolve the AAO template. The Cu nanowire
401 arrays were obtained after being washed with deionized water and dried with nitrogen gas. Finally, the
402 hydrophobic functionalization of NAMs was achieved by immersing the as-fabricated sample in a 2.5 mM
403 *n*-octadecanethiol ($\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{38}\text{S}$, Sigma–Aldrich, 98%) solution (dissolved in ethanol) at 70 °C for 1 h.

404 **Sample characterization**

405 The morphology of the samples was observed by a field-emission transmission scanning electron
406 microscope (FE-SEM, JSM-7610F) equipped with an energy-dispersive spectrometer (EDS, X-Max). The

407 surface wettability was characterized using a contact angle goniometer (Dataphysics, TBU100) at room
408 temperature (25 °C), with the probe liquid being 4 μL of deionized water. X-ray photoelectron
409 spectroscopy (XPS) data were collected on a Kratos AXIS Ultra spectrometer. X-ray diffraction (XRD)
410 patterns were recorded on a Shimadzu XRD-6000 X-ray diffractometer with a Cu $K\alpha$ source and a Rigaku
411 Miniflex 600 diffractometer.

412 **Electrochemical measurements**

413 The CO_2 electrochemical reduction reaction was carried out in a gas-phase-connected H-type
414 electrochemical cell with a standard three-electrode system connected to a potentiostat (Bio-Logic, VMP-
415 300) for data collection. Each compartment of the H-cell was filled with 40 mL electrolyte (0.1 M KHCO_3)
416 and separated by an anion exchange membrane (AEM, Fumasep FAS-50). Pt foil and Ag/AgCl electrode
417 filled with 3.5 M KCl solution were used as the counter electrode and the reference electrode, respectively.
418 Before the CO_2 RR test, CO_2 gas was bubbled into the electrolyte at a flow rate of $20 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ for 20 min
419 to saturate the electrolyte with CO_2 . The gas flow rate was controlled at 20 sccm during the test. The
420 cathodic electrodes were placed with a tilt angle of 30° such that the gas bubble flow from the bottom
421 could impact the electrode surface. The electrode potentials were rescaled to the reversible hydrogen
422 electrode (RHE) with iR compensation using the following equation:

$$423 \quad E_{\text{RHE}} = E_{\text{Ag/AgCl}} + 0.2046 + 0.0591 \times \text{pH} - IR \quad (1)$$

424 where I is the current and R is the internal resistance.

425 The ECSA values were estimated from double-layer capacitance (C_{dl}) currents at different scan rates
426 from 20 to $180 \text{ V} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. The C_{dl} values were achieved by a linear fit of the slope. The ECSA was then
427 determined from the difference between the capacitance of the NAMs relative to that of the Cu foil with
428 a surface area of 1 cm^2 .

429 CO stripping voltammetry was performed immediately after 40 min of CO₂RR at -1.2 V vs. RHE. CO
430 stripping chronoamperometry (CA) was performed by a 4-step CA sequence for double layer charging
431 correction⁶². A schematic illustration of this procedure is also shown in Supplementary Fig. 12. In step I,
432 we performed CO₂RR for 40 min at -1.2 V vs. RHE. During this step, the key intermediate CO* was
433 produced. In step II, the potential was switched to 0.2 V vs. RHE for 3 min. In this step, the current
434 included both electrode charging and CO oxidation until CO was depleted. In step III, the potential was
435 switched to -1.2 V vs. RHE again and sustained for 1 s, ensuring that the cathode was charged under the
436 same conditions as in step I. In step IV, the potential was set at 0.2 V vs. RHE for 3 min, under which the
437 current represents the electrode charging solely because negligible CO was produced in a 1 s CO₂RR
438 process. Thus, the difference between steps II and IV represents the net CO stripping current.

439 **Product analysis**

440 Gas-phase products were quantified using a gas chromatograph (GC, Shimadzu, 2014C). Liquid-phase
441 products were detected by a ¹H nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectrometer (Bruker, 400 MHz). The
442 FE was calculated based on the following equation:

$$443 \quad FE(\%) = \frac{n_{\text{product}} \times n_{\text{electrons}} \times F}{It} \quad (2)$$

444 where n_{product} is the product measured (mol), $n_{\text{electrons}}$ is the number of transferred electrons for the
445 generation of the product, F is the Faraday constant ($\text{C}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$), I is the current, and t is the reaction time
446 for the collected products.

447 **Laser scanning confocal microscopy**

448 The gas–liquid–solid interfaces were directly observed through a series of confocal images at different
449 depths within the nanowire arrays. All measurements were carried out on a laser scanning confocal
450 microscope (Leica, Stellaris 8) equipped with a $\times 63$ water objective lens. Rhodamine B was used as the

451 fluorescent dye for imaging the electrolyte at a concentration of $1 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$. Accordingly, a 540 nm laser
452 was used as the excitation source. The reflection and emission signals were recorded. The confocal images
453 were then obtained by overlaying the reflection and emission signals.

454 **Computational modeling**

455 To clarify the underlying mechanism by which the microscopic wetting state boosts CO_2RR
456 performance, we carried out a three-dimensional and steady-state numerical simulation of the mass
457 transfer process in CO_2RR to determine the distribution of pH, CO_2 concentration, and fluxes of species
458 involved in chemical equilibria within the structure under the applied operating conditions by exploiting
459 the finite-element method on the COMSOL Multiphysics[®] platform.^{50,51}

460 In this model, the electroreactions of CO_2RR and HER in 0.1 M KHCO_3 saturated with CO_2 at -1.2 V
461 vs. RHE; the carbonate species equilibria of OH^- , CO_2 , HCO_3^- , and CO_3^{2-} ; the mass diffusion of CO_2 ,
462 OH^- , H^+ , K^+ , HCO_3^- , and CO_3^{2-} ; and the local hydrolysis of K^+ in the electrolyte phase are considered.

463 The assumptions involved in this model are as follows: (1) The mass transfer processes are in a steady
464 state, and diffusion occurs near the surface with negligible convection. (2) CO_2RR and HER occur at the
465 liquid–solid interface, and the CO_2RR and HER-induced mass consumption (CO_2) and generation (OH^-)
466 are presented. (3) Because of the Cassie-Baxter wetting state and the stable CO_2 gas layer underneath the
467 nanowires, a constant concentration condition of saturated CO_2 is at the gas–liquid interface of NAM-30.
468 (4) Due to the partial wetting of NAM-10, *i.e.*, gas layer is underneath the nanowires at some sites and
469 liquid fulfills the nanowires at other sites, we carried out the two different simulations of the above two
470 cases and used the average value for comparison among the different samples. (5) In the NAM-0 model,
471 the electrolyte is filled with nanowires as a result of the Wenzel wetting state.

472 The governing equation of the mass transfer processes can be described by the Nernst–Planck equation,

473
$$N_i = -D_i \nabla c_i - z_i \frac{D_i}{RT} F c_i \nabla \phi \quad (3)$$

474 where the first and second terms represent the mass transfer induced by the concentration gradient and ion
 475 migration under the electric field, respectively. At steady state, the governing equations for the different
 476 species can be expressed by,

477
$$\nabla \left(-D_{\text{CO}_2} \nabla c_{\text{CO}_2} \right) = k_{1r} c_{\text{HCO}_3^-} - k_{1f} c_{\text{CO}_2} c_{\text{OH}^-} \quad (4)$$

478
$$\nabla \left(-D_{\text{HCO}_3^-} \nabla c_{\text{HCO}_3^-} - z_{\text{HCO}_3^-} \frac{D_{\text{HCO}_3^-}}{RT} F c_{\text{HCO}_3^-} \nabla \phi \right) =$$

$$k_{1f} c_{\text{CO}_2} c_{\text{OH}^-} - k_{1r} c_{\text{HCO}_3^-} + k_{2r} c_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}} - k_{2f} c_{\text{HCO}_3^-} c_{\text{OH}^-} \quad (5)$$

479
$$\nabla \left(-D_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}} \nabla c_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}} - z_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}} \frac{D_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}}}{RT} F c_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}} \nabla \phi \right) = k_{2f} c_{\text{HCO}_3^-} c_{\text{OH}^-} - k_{2r} c_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}} \quad (6)$$

480
$$\nabla \left(-D_{\text{OH}^-} \nabla c_{\text{OH}^-} - z_{\text{OH}^-} \frac{D_{\text{OH}^-}}{RT} F c_{\text{OH}^-} \nabla \phi \right) = k_{1r} c_{\text{HCO}_3^-} - k_{1f} c_{\text{CO}_2} c_{\text{OH}^-} + k_{2r} c_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}} - k_{2f} c_{\text{HCO}_3^-} c_{\text{OH}^-} \quad (7)$$

481 To solve the above equations, several boundary conditions are adopted, as shown in Supplementary
 482 Fig. 15. Bulk conditions (1), *i.e.*, a constant concentration of species, are considered at the top end of the
 483 electrolyte.

484
$$c_i = \text{cons.} (i = \text{CO}_2, \text{HCO}_3^-, \text{HCO}_3^{2-}, \text{OH}^-, \text{K}^+) \quad (8)$$

485 Symmetric condition (2), *i.e.*, zero flux of all species, are imposed at the lateral wall of the electrolyte
 486 to reflect the periodic 1/6 (60°) of the circumferential nanowire array and the symmetric V-shaped groove.

487
$$N_i = -D_i \nabla c_i - z_i \frac{D_i}{RT} F c_i \nabla \phi = 0 \quad (9)$$

488 At the boundaries of the nanowire surface (3), zero-flux conditions are adopted for nonreactive species,

489
$$N_i = -D_i \nabla c_i - z_i \frac{D_i}{RT} F c_i \nabla \phi = 0 (i = \text{HCO}_3^-, \text{HCO}_3^{2-}, \text{K}^+) \quad (10)$$

490 while reaction conditions are imposed for CO₂ and OH⁻, which are involved in CO₂RR and HER,
 491 respectively. The reactions occurring at the solid–liquid interface can be determined by the Nernst
 492 equation and the applied electrode potential,

$$493 \quad E_{\text{eq}} = E_{\text{eq}}^0 - \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \left(\frac{c_{\text{OH}^-}^n}{c_{\text{CO}_2}^m} \right) \quad (11)$$

494 For the CO₂RR, a first-order dependence of the CO₂ consumption rate on the concentration is assumed.
 495 Consequently, the boundary condition for consumption of CO₂ at the solid–liquid interface can be
 496 expressed by

$$497 \quad N_i = -D_{\text{CO}_2} \nabla c_{\text{CO}_2} = k_{\text{CO}_2} c_{\text{CO}_2} \quad (12)$$

498 The rate constant k_{CO_2} can be obtained by coupling the electron transfer (partial current density of
 499 products) and the mass conservation (FE of products) acquired from the experimental results,

$$500 \quad \left(\frac{j}{F} \right) \sum_k \frac{\text{FE}_k \cdot m_k}{z_k} = \iiint_{l-s \text{ interface}} k_{\text{CO}_2} c_{\text{CO}_2} dx dy dz \quad (13)$$

501 A zero-order dependence of the OH⁻ generation rate on the concentration is assumed. Similarly, the
 502 boundary condition for OH⁻ can be obtained by,

$$503 \quad N_i = -D_{\text{OH}^-} \nabla c_{\text{OH}^-} = k_{\text{OH}^-, \text{CO}_2\text{RR}} c_{\text{CO}_2} + k_{\text{OH}^-, \text{HER}} \quad (14)$$

504 The rate constant k_{OH^-} can be obtained by coupling electron transfer (partial current density of products)
 505 and mass conservation (FE of products),

$$506 \quad \left(\frac{j}{F} \right) \sum_k \frac{\text{FE}_k \cdot m_k}{z_k} = \iiint_{l-s \text{ interface}} k_{\text{OH}^-, \text{CO}_2\text{RR}} c_{\text{CO}_2} dx dy dz \quad (15)$$

$$507 \quad \left(\frac{j}{F} \right) \frac{\text{FE}_{\text{H}_2} \cdot m_{\text{H}_2}}{z_{\text{H}_2}} = \iiint_{l-s \text{ interface}} k_{\text{OH}^-, \text{HER}} dx dy dz \quad (16)$$

508 The buffer effect of K⁺ near the surface due to the electric potential can be described by,⁶³⁻⁶⁴

509

510 The reactions toward different products detected in experiments and corresponding stoichiometric
511 parameters are given in Supplementary Table 2. The equilibria involving the protonation/ deprotonation
512 of species in solution, the corresponding forward and backward reaction rate constants, and the reaction
513 equilibrium constants are listed in Supplementary Tables 3 and 4, respectively. The diffusion coefficients
514 and bulk concentrations (initial concentrations) for the involved species in the model are listed in
515 Supplementary Table 5.

516 The set of above equations with boundary conditions forms a closed system for the calculation of the
517 concentrations of all the species involved in the three-dimensional system.

518 **Data availability**

519 The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon
520 reasonable request.

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696 **Author contributions**

697 Y.C., X.M., B.L., and A.B.W. conceived the initial idea for this research. A.B.W. guided this work. Y.C.,
698 M.I.B.S., and Q.L. designed and fabricated the samples. Y.C. and C.W. characterized the samples. Y.C.
699 and M.I.B.S. performed the CO₂ electroreduction reaction experiments. Y.C. and Q.W. carried out the
700 data analysis. Y.C. and Q.L. performed the finite element simulation. All the authors are responsible for
701 writing the paper and have approved the final version of the manuscript.

702 **Competing interests**

703 The authors declare no competing interests.

704 **Additional information**

705 **Supplementary information** is available for this paper.

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707 **Figure legends**

708 **Fig. 1 | Schematic illustration of the tunable hierarchical structure design and corresponding**
709 **preparation strategy for enhancing CO₂ mass transfer and optimizing the local microenvironment.**

710 **a**, Liquid–solid–gas three-phase schematic highlighting that by tuning hierarchically structures, the
711 wetting state and the mass transport near the liquid-gas interface are adaptively changed. The
712 microgrooves exert upward Laplace pressure and stabilize the Cassie-Baxter wetting state, which enhances
713 the diffusion of the gaseous reactants from the bottom gas layer to the top reaction zone. Sparsely arranged
714 nanowires at the bottom assist in reducing the lateral diffusion resistance of gas molecules. Conversely,
715 densely packed nanowires at the top confine the key intermediate CO* and facilitate C-C coupling for
716 multicarbon products. **b**, Schematic illustration of the realization method of hierarchically structured
717 NAMs.

718 **Fig. 2 | Characterization of NAMs.** Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of NAMs with opening
719 angles of **a**, 30°, **b**, 10°, and **c**, 0° for the microgrooves. The first and second columns show the nanowire
720 arrays with microgrooves from the top and side views, respectively. The third and fourth columns show
721 the densely packed nanowires at the top and sparsely arranged nanowires at the bottom, respectively. **d**,
722 The contact angles for the superhydrophobic NAMs and hydrophobic Cu foil. **e**, High-resolution XPS Cu
723 2*p* spectra of NAMs before (blue) and after (red) hydrophobic treatment. **f**, High-resolution XPS S 2*p*
724 spectra of NAMs before (blue) and after (red) hydrophobic treatment.

725 **Fig. 3 | CO₂RR performance of NAMs in a CO₂-saturated 0.1 M KHCO₃ electrolyte.** **a**, Product
726 selectivity of NAM-30 as a function of applied potential. **b**, The product distribution of all samples at -1.2
727 V vs. RHE. **c**, Ratio of carbon reduction products to hydrogen at -1.2 V vs. RHE. **d**, Ratio of C₂₊ products
728 to C₁ products at -1.2 V vs. RHE. **e**, Calculation of C_{d1} based on the current densities and scan rates of the
729 corresponding cyclic voltammetry (CV) curves. **f**, Comparison of the geometric area- and ECSA-
730 normalized partial current density of the CO₂RR for all samples at -1.2 V vs. RHE.

731 **Fig. 4 | Characterization of gas–liquid–solid interfaces for NAMs during the CO₂RR.** **a**, Optical
732 observation of the macroscopic wetting states of NAMs in the CO₂RR. **b**, Confocal microscopy images of

733 NAM-30, NAM-10, and NAM-0. The slices are displayed from a top view and selected along the height
734 direction of the nanowires. The red signal represents the emission light of the rhodamine dissolved in the
735 electrolyte, while the green signal is the reflection of the excitation laser light from gas–liquid–solid
736 interfaces. **c-d**, Schematic illustration of the gas–liquid–solid three-phase interfaces of NAM-30 and
737 NAM-0 in the CO₂RR. **e**, Charge of CO oxidation derived from chronoamperometric curves.

738 **Fig. 5 | 3D numerical simulation of the mass transfer process on NAMs in the CO₂RR.** **a**, Physical
739 model schematic of the mass transfer processes in the CO₂RR. **b**, Contour maps of the CO₂ concentration
740 profile on NAM-30 in 3D and 2D views of the left and right columns, respectively. The 2D plot is the
741 cross-sectional view labeled by a dashed line in the 3D map. The streamlines indicate the direction of CO₂
742 transfer. **c**, Contour maps of the CO₂ concentration profile of NAM-0. **d**, Contour maps of the pH of NAM-
743 30. The streamlines indicate the direction of H⁺ transfer. **e**, Contour maps of the effect of pH on NAM-0.
744 **f**, Local concentration distribution of CO₂ along the height direction of the nanowires. **g**, Local pH
745 distribution along the height direction of the nanowires. **h**, Comparison of the spatially averaged
746 concentrations of CO₂ and pH among the NAMs. All the results were acquired at -1.2 V vs. RHE.

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